

Chemical Investigation of *Colocasia antiquorum* Schott.

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The rhizome of *Colocasia antiquorum* (syn.: *C. esculenta* Linn.) Schott. (Araceae) has styptic, stimulant and rubefacient action and is used in scorpion sting¹. The pressed juice of the petioles has been recommended as styptic and stringent². Survey of the literature reveals the presence of sterols^{3,4}, anthocyanidin glycosides⁵, fatty acids⁶ and mucilage⁷ in the plant. From the tubers of the native plant five new aliphatic constituents along with known compounds namely nonacosane, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, cyanidin-3-glucoside and two other components in trace amounts have been isolated.

Chloroform extract of the tubers (2 kg) was chromatographed on silica gel with petrol. The initial petrol fractions yielded compound 1 and nonacosane. Gradual increment of polarity of petrol with CHCl_3 afforded compounds 2–5, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol. Cyanidin-3-glucoside was obtained in CHCl_3 -MeOH (9 : 1) mixture. The physical and spectroscopic data for nonacosane, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and cyanidin-3-glucoside agreed with those reported in the literature.

Compound 1, m.p. 62–63°, $[M]^+$ at m/z 368 ($\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$), decolourised bromine water. Its ir spectrum showed absorption at 3420 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl group. Its ^1H nmr spectrum displayed signals for the presence of a methyl group (δ 0.87, brs), 19 methylene groups (δ 1.30, brs), two D_2O exchangeable protons (δ 2.36, s, $2 \times \text{OH}$), one geminal proton attached to hydroxyl group (δ 3.20), two hydroxymethylene protons (δ 3.76 and 3.90) and a multiplet at δ 5.20. On the basis of these studies, it was concluded that the compound is an open chain unsaturated diol possessing one primary

and one secondary hydroxy groups. The precise nature of the compound was largely elicited from its mass spectrum. Besides the molecular ion peak, the spectrum exhibited significant peaks at m/z 350 $[M-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$, 337 $[M-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}]^+$, 323 $[M-\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2]^+$, 300, 295, 284, 83, 68 and 43 (Scheme 1) along with many peaks with uniform loss of 14 mass units⁸. On acetylation, compound 1 furnished a diacetylated product, ν_{max} (KBr) 1725 cm^{-1} , m/z $[M]^+$ 452. Hence, the structure of 1 is established as tetracos-20-en-1,18-diol.

Compound 2, m.p. 73–74°, $[M]^+$ at m/z 450 ($\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}$) had an important ir band at 1720 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of a keto group. Its ^1H nmr spectrum exhibited the presence of two terminal methyl groups (δ 0.50, s), one secondary methyl group (δ 1.0, t, J 3.5 Hz), 26 methylene groups (δ 1.22, brs), two adjacent methylene groups attached to the carbonyl group (δ 1.90) and a methine proton (δ 2.20, q). Its mass spectrum suggested the presence of ion peaks at m/z 352, 323, 295, 155, 127 and 98 (Scheme 1) in addition to many peaks with uniform loss of 14 m.u.⁸. Treatment of 2 with DNP formed a yellow coloured derivative. Hence, the structure of 2 is formulated as 25-methyltriacont-10-one.

Compound 3, m.p. 72–73°, $[M]^+$ at m/z 424 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_2$), had ir band at 3400 cm^{-1} for a hydroxyl group. Its ^1H nmr spectrum showed the diagnostic signals for one methyl group (δ 0.70, s), 23 methylenes (δ 1.23, brs), two hydroxymethylene protons (δ 3.46 and 3.60, m), one proton geminal to hydroxyl group (δ 3.22, m) and two ethylene protons (δ 4.57, m). Its mass spectrum exhibited ion peaks at m/z 392, 281, 255, 225, 199, 169 and 143

Scheme 1

(Scheme 1) in addition to many uniform loss of 14 m.u.^o. Acetylation of 3 with Ac₂O-pyridine afforded a diacetylated product, ν_{max} (KBr) 1725 cm⁻¹; m/z (rel. int.) 508 (1.6). Hence, the structure of 3 is established as octacos-10-en-1,12-diol.

Compound 4, m.p. 68–69° [M]⁺ at m/z 504, (C₂₈H₅₆O), demonstrated the presence of a hydroxyl group at 3430 cm⁻¹ in its ir spectrum. Its ¹H nmr spectrum displayed signals for one methyl group

(δ 0.86, s), 29 methylene functions (δ 1.23, brs), one D₂O displaceable proton for hydroxyl function (δ 2.06, brs), five methylene protons (δ 2.26, t, J 5.2 Hz) and terminal methylene protons (δ 4.33, m; 4.96, m). Its mass spectrum showed ion fragments at 486 [M -H₂O]⁺, 477 [M -CH=CH]⁺, in addition to 395, 367, 137 and 109 (Scheme 1) and uniform loss of 14 m.u.^o. Acetylation of 4 with Ac₂O-pyridine yielded a monoacetyl derivative, ν_{max} (KBr)

1730 cm^{-1} . Hence, the structure of 4 is established as pentatriacont-1,7-dien-12-ol.

Compound 5, m.p. 83–84°, had $[M]^+$ at m/z 524 ($\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{68}\text{O}_3$). Its ir spectrum indicated the existence of hydroxyl groups at 3445 cm^{-1} . Its ^1H nmr spectrum displayed the presence of two methyls (δ 0.90, s), 2 δ methylenes (δ 1.0, brs), two D_2O exchangeable protons (δ 2.20, brs), one methine proton (δ 2.36, m), three protons geminal to hydroxyl groups (δ 3.30, brs; 3.60, m) and two olefinic protons (δ 4.46, m). Its mass spectrum exhibited ion fragments at m/z 506 $[M-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$, 412, 396, 356, 350, 320, 195, 174, 168, 128 and 112 as well as numerous ion peaks formed due to expulsion of 14 m.u.⁸. Acetylation of 5 yielded a triacetyl derivative, ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 and 1715 cm^{-1} , m/z 650. Hence, structure 5 for the aliphatic hydrocarbon is established as 25-methyl-tritriacont-21-en-1,9,11-triol.

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